

GROWTH AND YIELD OF CUCUMBER VARIETIES AS INFLUENCED BY PRUNING AT ABAKALIKI AGRICULTURAL AREA, SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The effect of pruning on the growth and yield of four cucumber varieties was evaluated using a 4 x 2 factorial laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). Market more 76, Marketer and Point-sett varieties produced significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher total and marketable yield than Market more 70. Similar trend was observed for total and marketable fruit weight, and marketable fruit number per plant. Significant differences in some vegetative growth parameters were found between the cucumber varieties. Market more 76 and Marketer varieties had similar but significantly ($p < 0.01$) shorter days to 50% anthesis than Market more 70 followed by Point-sett. Marketer had significantly ($p < 0.05$) longer stem length than the other cucumber varieties. Market more 76 and Marketer varieties produced similar, but significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher number of branches per plant than Market more 70 and Point Sett. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in terms of yield and yield components were found between the two pruning treatments. The no pruning treatment produced the highest total yield and total fruit number per plant. The pruning treatment produced the highest marketable fruit yield, total and marketable fruit weight, and marketable fruit number per plant. Pruning significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected the days to 50% anthesis and stem length. Unpruned cucumber varieties took shorter days of 26 for the 50% of the plants to flower while pruned cucumber varieties produced longer stem lengths of 18.46 than the non pruned treatment.

KEYWORDS: Cucumber, pruning, vegetative growth and yield.

INTRODUCTION

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* Linn.) is one of the most popular members of the cucurbitaceae (Vine crop) family. Written evidence indicates that cucumber originated in India, which spread westward and became popular throughout the Egyptian and the Greek-Roman eras (Nonnecke, 1992). The crop is cultivated in most parts of Northern Nigeria and some parts of Eastern Nigeria by peasant farmers who lack information on some important cultural practices. This has resulted in very low yield and the production of fruits with yellow bellies, which are highly unmarketable (Ekwu, *et al.*, 2007).

The significance of yield may be qualified by factors such as fruit quality, fruit size, or price development of the market determined by season. Fruit exceeding a certain size are of no value, and nowadays, consumers demand good fruit shape and quality (Than, 1996). The growth of plants and other factors can be modified by pruning to suit human needs and desires (Than, 1996). Pruning is the act of cutting off plant branches or twigs so as to encourage fruiting or flowering. Shoots, foliage, flower and fruit are pruned to maintain a proper balance between the vegetative growth and fruit load so as to maximize production (Wayne, 1990). There are many purposes for cucumber vine pruning treatments. These are for mechanical harvesting, hybrid seed production, to easily control insect and disease, to use the higher plant population without significant yield reduction, and to obtain uniform fruits (Humphries and Vermillion, 1994). Gobeil and Gosselin (1990) asserted that plant density and pruning are two factors which most likely affect productivity of cucumber. However, the effects of these factors are also dependent on soil regime, vigour of the variety or strain and the cultural management being used. Palada and Chang (2003) reported that the removal of the lateral shoot had a positive effect on the total yield of cucumbers. The first four to six lateral runners that appear should be removed while the other runners above should be allowed to run (Douglas and Larry, 2001).

The objective of this study was therefore to determine the effects of pruning on the vegetative growth, yield and yield components of four cucumber varieties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of Crop Production and Landscape Management, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki (Lat. 06°04'N; Long. 18°65'E) from June 2008 to September 2008, which was repeated from June 2009 to September 2009 in the second year cropping season. The mean monthly rainfall during 2008 is 153.41 and that of 2009 is 162.10. The mean minimum / maximum temperature and relative humidity in 2008 are 21.14 / 29.49 °C and 76.14% and in 2009, 21.43 / 29.71 °C and 80.14%. The soil is shallow with unconsolidated parent material (shale residuum) within 1m of the soil surface and classified as Dystric leptosol (Anikwe *et al.*, 1999). The soil was formerly cultivated with yam, cassava and maize intercrop but had been under grass-legume fallow for 2 years before the start of the experiment.

Data sets analyzed for this study were collected from an experiment originally designed as 4 x 2 factorial laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD). The eight treatments combination consisted of two pruning methods [no pruning (P₀) and 4 - lateral stem pruning i.e. pruning out the lateral branches on main stem from node 4 down (P₁)] and four cucumber varieties (Market more 70, Market more 76, Marketer and Point-sett). The experimental field measured 26 m x 20 m (520 m²) and it was divided into four equal replicates, 1 m apart. Each replicate consisted of 8 plots, giving a total of 32 test plots. Each plot measured 2 m x 2 m with 0.5 m between adjacent plots.

The seeds were sown into well prepared raised beds on June 16, 2008 and June 5, 2009 for the two year trials with recommended spacing of 50 x 50 cm² per hill. Seedlings were thinned twice, and kept one plant per hill before 3 true leaf stages. 187 kg ha⁻¹ each of N, P and K was added to the soil using N-P-K (15-15-15) as basal fertilizer application. A further 65 kg N ha⁻¹ was split applied at 3 and 6 weeks after sowing (WAS) as top dressing using urea (46 % N) as the nitrogen source.

Staking with bamboo sticks was done 3 WAS when the tendrils began to appear while the stems were tied onto the sticks with loosen threads. Weeding was carried out at 3 and 6 WAS to control weeds and mixture of Benomyl (Benlate) and Dithane M45 was sprayed to the crop weekly starting from 3 WAS as a routine preventive measure against fungal foliar diseases. Insecticide, Instakill 35 Emulsifiable concentrate was sprayed at 1st, 3rd and 5th WAS. Pruning was done 4 WAS before flower initiation. Harvesting commenced 8 WAS, thereafter at 2 days interval.

Six randomly selected plants were used for the determination of vegetative growth (days to 50% anthesis, stem length (cm), number of branches per plant and days to harvest); yield components {number of fruits per plant and fruit weight per plant (kg)} and yield was computed from fruits harvested from the net plot and converted into tons per hectare. All data collected was subjected to statistical analysis of variance (combined for the two years) to test for the significance of treatment effects using GenStat 5.0 (2003).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Variety

The cucumber varieties differed significantly in some vegetative growth parameters like days to 50% anthesis, stem length and number of branches (Table 1). Market more 76 and Marketer varieties had similar but significantly (p<0.01) shorter days to 50% anthesis (21.67 and 23.00) than Market more 70 followed by Point-sett in that order. Marketer had significantly (p<0.05) longer stem length of 222.5 cm than the other cucumber varieties. Market more 76 and Marketer varieties produced similar, but significantly (p<0.05) higher number of branches per plant (8.17 and 7.50) than Market more 70 and Point Sett. These differentials of growth rates indices according to Ibrahim *et al.* (2001) are normally attributed to their genetic make up. Cucumber varieties also differ significantly in yield and yield components (Table 2). Market more 76, Marketer and Point-sett varieties produced similar, but significantly (p<0.05) higher total (22.50 t ha⁻¹, 21.75 t ha⁻¹ and 20.25 t ha⁻¹) and marketable yield (16.50 t ha⁻¹, 16.25 t ha⁻¹, and 14.75 t ha⁻¹) than Market more 70. Similar results were obtained for total and marketable fruit weight, and marketable fruit number per plant. Total and marketable yield (t/ha) and marketable number of fruits per plant which were observed to be highest in varieties Market more 76 > Marketer > Point-sett and Market more 70 least could be attributed to the fact that the first three varieties are semi-determinate (Market more 76, Marketer and Point-sett) and as such directed most of their nutrient flow to their reproductive growth (in this case fruits) unlike Market more 70 which is an indeterminate variety whose nature is such that vegetative growth does not terminate at the onset of

reproductive growth and has to share its nutrient flow both ways (Bodunde *et al.*, 1993; Ibrahim, 1994). The higher average total and marketable fruit weight per plant (kg) recorded by Market more 76, Marketer and Point-sett than Market more 70 could be attributed to the fact that the former have bigger fruits (in terms of size) than the latter.

Effect of Pruning

Pruning significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected the days to 50% anthesis and stem length (Table 1). Unpruned cucumber varieties took shorter days (26 days) to 50% anthesis. This is in agreement with the work of Than (1996) who reported that pruning prolonged number of days to flowering. Pruned cucumber varieties produced longer stem lengths of 18.46 than the unpruned ones. This is because pruning maintains a proper balance between the vegetative growth and fruit load so as to maximize production (Humphries and Vermillion, 1994). Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in terms of yield and yield components were found between the two pruning treatments (Table 2). The non pruning treatment produced the highest total yield (21.50 t ha^{-1}) and total fruit number per plant (11.00). The pruning treatment produced the highest marketable fruit yield (15.75 t ha^{-1}), total and marketable fruit weight (1.73 kg and 1.45 kg) and marketable fruit number per plant of 8.50. These could be attributed to the more availability of nutrients, water and light to plants under pruning for marketable fruits yield, weight, fruit number and total fruit weight, and lack of pruning for non marketable fruits yield, weight and fruit number per plant (Humphries and Vermillion, 1994; Dao, 1996 and Duong, 1999).

Interaction

It was observed that pruning had no specific effect on the varieties tested or there was no pruning -variety interaction.

CONCLUSION

Pruning had significant effect on some vegetative parameters, yield and yield components tested. Thus there is need for pruning in other to increase marketable yield.

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Table 1. Effects of cultivar and pruning on cucumber days to 50 % anthesis, stem length (cm), number of branches per plant and days to harvest.

Treatments	Days to 50% Anthesis	Stem Length (cm)	Number of Branches/Plant	Days to Harvest
Cultivar (C)				
Market more 70	28.67b	159.4b	5.79b	53.33
Market more 76	23.00c	162.1b	8.17a	55.67
Marketer	21.67c	222.5a	7.50a	60.33
Point Sett	32.33a	164.3b	5.33b	58.00
F-LSD _(0.05)	2.354**	42.10*	1.601*	Ns
Pruning (P)				
No Pruning	26b	163.5b	6.42	55.67
4-Stem Pruning	29a	184.6a	7.08	58.00
F-LSD _(0.05)	1.664*	18.77*	Ns	Ns
Interactions				
C x P	ns	ns	Ns	Ns

Table 2. Effects of cultivar and pruning on cucumber fruit number per plant, fruit weight per plant (kg) and yield (t/ha)

Treatments	Fruit Number/Plant			Fruit Weight (kg)			Yield (t/ha)		
	Marketable	Non Marketable	Total	Marketable	Non Marketable	Total	Marketable	Non Marketable	Total
Cultivar									
Market more 70	7.67b	2.50	10.17	0.90b	0.38	1.28b	13.50b	5.75	19.25b
Market more 76	8.57a	2.17	10.74	1.10a	0.40	1.50a	16.50a	6.00	22.50a
Marketer	8.50a	3.00	11.50	1.08a	0.37	1.45a	16.25a	5.50	21.75a
Point Sett	8.33a	2.83	11.16	0.98a	0.37	1.35a	14.75a	5.50	20.25a
F-LSD _(0.05)	0.63*	ns	ns	0.14*	ns	0.16*	2.13*	Ns	2.42*
Pruning									
No Pruning	8.00b	3.00a	11.00a	0.98b	0.38a	1.36b	14.75b	6.75	21.50a
4-Stem Pruning	8.50a	1.39b	9.89b	1.44a	0.29b	1.73a	15.75a	4.63	20.38b
F-LSD _(0.05)	0.13*	0.79*	0.92*	0.24*	0.07*	0.31*	1.50*	ns	0.91*
Interactions									
C x P	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns

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